

NITROGEN AND SULPHUR CO-DOPED CARBON NANO DOTS FROM VIBURNUM GRANDIFLORUM FRUIT AND THEIR APPLICATION IN DETECTION OF Fe^{3+} IN AQUEOUS MEDIUM

Akhtar Ali Khan¹, Ihsanullah², Najeeb-ur-Rehman³, Shaukat Ali Khan⁴, Attaullah⁵,
Muhammed Umer⁶, Babar Khan⁷

¹Institute of Chemical Sciences (ICS), University of Swat, Pakistan.

^{2,3,6}Associate professor Institute of Chemical Sciences (ICS), University of Swat, Pakistan.

⁴Center for Animal Sciences and Fisheries, University of Swat, Pakistan.

⁵Department of Zoology, Abdul Wali Khan University Mardan, Pakistan

⁷Babar Khan Centre for Biotechnology and Microbiology (CB&M), University of Swat, Pakistan

¹alikhanakhtar356@gmail.com

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Corresponding Author: *

Akhtar Ali Khan

Abstract

The number 10^9 is termed the word Nano, nanoparticles are particles made up of carbon, metal, metal oxides or organic matter and typically less than 100 nanometers in size. The nanoparticles are generally classified into the organic and inorganic nanoparticles, ceramics and carbon based nanoparticles with chemical variation base. The organic nanoparticles completely made of carbon are carbon-based nanoparticles and they can be classified into variant allotropic forms like fullerenes, graphene, carbon nanotubes, carbon nanofibers, carbon nano-dots and carbon black and sometimes activated carbon in nano scale size. Quantum dots are nanoscale made crystal having unique electronic and optical properties that is ability to transport electrons and emit light of various color, blue, yellow and orange, when illuminated by UV light source. Carbon based quantum dots are younger member of carbonaceous nanoparticle belong to broad family of carbon allotrope and generally called Carbon dots (CDs) are novel zero dimensional nanostructure (<10 nm in size) carbon based particles with lattice space of 0.24 and 0.34 nm accidentally developed in 2004 by Xu et al. Carbon dots are common name for variety of extremely tiny size carbon nanomaterial, graphene quantum dots and carbon quantum dots are two most common types of Carbon quantum dots. Because of their chemical, biological and pharmaceutical importance there has been considerable interest in developing numerous preparation approaches since their discovery. Literature survey report reveals that various plant resources such as orange, banana and banana peel, watermelon, *Trapa bispinosa* peel, coffee grounds, food waste, sugar cane juice, potato, ginger juice, orange waste peels, bread, sugar, and jiggery as natural carbon source and milk, hair, honey etc. as animals precursors are checked via several preparative techniques, arc discharge, laser ablation, and electrochemical oxidation, microwave mediated synthesis, thermal decomposition and hydrothermal method, to synthesize C-Dots. The specie, *Viburnum grandiflorum*, is folk medicinal plant which is used locally to treat stomach and toothache, abdominal pain, malarial,

diuretic, wound healing and whooping cough. It has also been evaluated as respiratory diseases, as anti-typhoid and analgesic, cytotoxic, as anti-diabetic, antioxidant and anti-bacterial, anti-cancer, as anti-nociceptive and as molluscicide agent due to having natural product. The selected species possess a lot of natural products. After the literature study a facile synthesis of fluorescence N/S Co-doped carbon dots was carried out from fruit of *Viburnum grandiflorum* using L-Cysteine as Sulphur source and ethylenediamine as Nitrogen source was performed through hydrothermal treatment and the synthesized N/S CDs was apply to check heavy metals detection in water, especially Fe³⁺ sensing activity. The C-dots functional groups were acquired with help of a FTIR (Perkin Elmer spectrometer). The absorption spectra of C-dots U – 300 spectrophotometer (Hitachi Japan) and fluorescence spectra (FL) were performed on (Shimadzu RF – 530l) fluorescence spectrofluorometer. The Bruker AXSD8 Advance X-ray diffractometer was used to record crystalline structure of synthesized C-dots and XPS tech was conducted on Quentera SXM (ULVAC-PH1 Japan) XPS. The morphology of C-dots was examined by the field emission scanning electron microscopy (HITACHI H-8100 Tokyo, Japan) and particle size was examined by TEM (JEOL-2100+).

Graphical abstract

1.1 INTRODUCTION:

The number 10⁹ is termed the word Nano which shows the 1 billionth of any unit that gives the formation of one dimensional (1D) very tiny particle [1-3]. Nanoparticles are the fundamental components of nanotechnology a interested and famous emerging field of research in science since the 20th century after Richard P.

Feynman introduced the term nanotechnology in his lecture there is plenty of room at the bottom in 1959 [4, 5]. Nanoparticles are particles consist of carbon, metal & metal oxides, organic substances and typically less than 100 nanometers in size [6, 7]. The nanoparticles due to larger surface area to the volume, good mechanical

strength and increased stability in a chemical reactions, have different optical, physical, mechanical properties and chemical, biological properties as compared to their respective particles of large scales and these properties of nanoparticles has led to their uses in various objects such as cooking vessel, electronics, renewable energy and in aerospace industry and key for a clean as well as sustainable future [8-11]. They are different in dimension, shape, size, surface, structure and chemical composition, and can be either a zero-dimensional to one, two or three-dimensional on the basis of dimension [12-14]. On the basis of shape variation it can be classified as spherical shape, cylindrical shape, tubular shape, conical shape, hollow core shape, spiral shape and flat shape [15]. Nanoparticle can be a uniform or irregular with surface and some nanoparticles are crystalline or amorphous with structural variation. The nanoparticles are generally classified into the organic and inorganic nanoparticles, ceramics and carbon based with chemical variation base Fig 1.1 [16]. Organic Dendrimers (a), organic micelles, liposomes (b) and ferritin (c) nanoparticles are commonly categorized the polymers or organic nanoparticles Fig 1.2. These nanoparticles are not hazardous and are biodegradable and

micelles and liposomes like particle possess a hollow core [17, 18]. Inorganic nanoparticles are metal and metal oxide particles that are not made up of carbon (element other than carbon). The inorganic nanoparticles are not toxic, biocompatible and hydrophilic and most stable than organic nanoparticles. Nanoparticles that are synthesized from metals, aluminum (Al), cadmium (Cd), cobalt (Co), copper (Cu), gold (Au), iron (Fe), lead (Pb), silver (Ag) and zinc (Zn), to nano metric sizes either by destructive or constructive methods are metal based nanoparticles [19-22]. The metal-based nanoparticles are oxidized in presence of oxygen to metal oxide base nanoparticles to modify the reactivity and efficiency properties of their respective metal-based nanoparticles. The commonly modify metal to metal oxide are Al_2O_3 (Aluminium oxide), CeO_2 (Cerium oxide), Fe_2O_3 (Iron oxide), Fe_3O_4 (Magnetite), SiO_2 (Silicon dioxide), TiO_2 (Titanium oxide), ZnO (Zinc oxide) [23-26]. The ceramics nanoparticles are also known as nonmetallic solid are synthesized through heating or successive cooling and may be in polycrystalline form, amorphous form, porous form, dens or hollow form [27, 28].

Figure 1.1: Classification of Nanoparticles

The organic nanoparticles are completely carbon containing nanoparticles or made of carbon and they can be classified into variant allotropic forms like fullerenes, graphene, carbon nanotubes, carbon nanofibers, carbon nano dots and carbon black and sometimes activated

carbon in nano scale [16, 29]. Fullerene allotropic form is a carbon molecule in hollow spherical, tubular or hollow ellipsoid shape made up carbon atoms held together by single and double bonds that is sp^2 hybridization. The connected sp^2 hybridized carbon atoms result in

formation of close or partially close mesh (cage structure) having fused pentagonal rings or heptagonal rings. The spherical shape fullerenes consist of about 28 to 1500 carbon atoms with diameters as low as 8.20 nm for a single layer and varying from 04 nm to 36 nm for multi-layered fullerenes **Fig 1.3 (a)** [30-32]. Graphene a two-dimensional surface carbon allotrope made up single layer of carbon atoms arranged in hexagonal network of honeycomb lattice. The name graphene suggests single layer graphite with double bonds. Graphene sheet is a monolayer graphite in which each atom is bonded to other three carbon atoms with single and numerous double bonds having around 1 nm thickness **Fig 1.3 (b)** [33]. Carbon nanotubes CNTs are hollow tubular nano size molecules consist of six fused rings carbon atoms in cylindrical form with different length from a few micrometers to several millimeters. Single wall carbon nanotubes with diameter 0.70 are formed by rolling up graphene sheet and multi-layer carbon nanotubes with diameter up to 100nm are composed of rolled up multi-layer graphene sheets **Fig 1.3 (c)** [34-36]. Carbon nanofibers

(CNFs) discovered by Ijima in 1991 are carbon base irregular cylindrical nanostructure tube of wrapped graphene sheets [37]. When graphene layers are arranged into stacked cones, stacked cups or stacked plate shapes with diameter from 05-100 nm and length 05-100 micrometers are called carbon nanofibers. The difference between Carbon nano fibers and Carbon NTs is in the present of a hollow cavity and the diameters of CNTs are generally smaller than those of the corresponding CNFs. Carbon Nanofibers are still very attractive because they have a relatively high specific surface area (up to 177 m² g) and uniform meso-porous magnitude and distribution. Carbon black nanoparticles are the nano amorphous powders material which is made up of carbon, also named with soot. The shape of carbon black is spherical having diameter size in ranges from 20 nm to 70 nm. Interaction is present between the particles and so bound in an aggregate (500 nm). Carbon blacks are used in copy machine inks and also used in laser printing. They also have applications as in rubber reinforcement preservatives as well as pigments in plastic industries **Fig 1.3 (e)** [38].

a

c

b

d

e

Figure 1.3: Fullerene (a), graphene (b), carbon tube (c), carbon fiber (d) and carbon black (e)

Figure 1.3: Organic nanoparticles

2. Material and Methods

2.1 Synthesis of (N, S-Co-doped) Carbon Nanodots

2.1.1 Synthesis of Carbon Nanodots from *Viburnum grandiflorum* Fruit Powder

Fresh fruits of *Viburnum grandiflorum* were shade-dried and ground into a fine powder using a stainless-steel mortar and pestle. One gram of the obtained fruit powder was dispersed in 25 mL of deionized (DI) water in a glass beaker and magnetically stirred for 15 min to obtain a homogeneous suspension. The mixture was then transferred into a 50 mL Teflon-lined stainless-steel autoclave and subjected to hydrothermal treatment at 180 °C for 7 h in an electric oven. After completion of the reaction, the autoclave was allowed to cool naturally to room temperature for 2–3 h. The resulting brownish solution was collected into Eppendorf tubes and centrifuged twice at 14,000 rpm for 14 min to remove large particulates. The supernatant was carefully collected using a

micropipette and further purified by filtration through a 0.22 μm syringe filter. To eliminate remaining low-molecular-weight impurities and soluble metal ions that could affect the optical properties of the carbon nanodots (CDs), the filtered solution was dialyzed against DI water using dialysis tubing with a molecular weight cut-off (MWCO) of 1000 Da for 56 h, with the dialysis water replaced every 8 h. The purified carbon nanodots were finally stored at temperatures below 4 °C for further use and characterization (Scheme 2.1).

2.1.2 Synthesis of N,S-Co-doped Carbon Nanodots Using *Viburnum grandiflorum*, Ethylenediamine, and L-Cysteine

For the synthesis of nitrogen and sulfur co-doped carbon nanodots (N,S-CDs), *Viburnum grandiflorum* fruit powder was prepared as described above. One gram of the powder was mixed with 25 mL of DI water, followed by the addition of 250 μL of ethylenediamine (EDA) as

a nitrogen source and 250 mg of L-cysteine as a sulfur source. Heteroatom co-doping with nitrogen and sulfur was employed to enhance the fluorescence properties and quantum yield of the carbon nanodots. The reaction mixture was magnetically stirred for 15 min to achieve homogeneity and then transferred into a 50 mL Teflon-lined autoclave. The autoclave was heated at 180 °C for 12 h in an electric oven. After cooling naturally to room temperature, the resulting brown solution was centrifuged twice at 14,000 rpm for 14 min. The supernatant was filtered through a 0.22 μm syringe filter to remove residual large particles. The filtered N,S-CDs solution was purified by dialysis (MWCO 1000 Da) against DI water for 56 h, with the dialysis water changed every 8 h. This step ensured the removal of unreacted precursors and soluble impurities that may interfere with

fluorescence behavior. The purified N,S-CDs were stored in a refrigerator at temperatures below 4 °C for subsequent characterization and applications (Scheme 2.2). To optimize the experimental conditions, various synthesis parameters were systematically varied, including the amount of fruit powder (1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, and 3.5 g), L-cysteine concentration (50, 100, 150, 200, 250, and 300 mg), ethylenediamine dosage (50, 100, 200, 250, and 300 μL), reaction temperature (140, 190, 220, and 240 °C), and reaction time (4, 8, 10, 12, and 16 h). Except for these variations, all other synthesis and purification steps remained identical to those described above.

Figure 2.1. Schematic illustration of the formation of carbon quantum dots from *Viburnum grandiflorum* via the hydrothermal method.

Figure 2.1: Formation of CQ-Dots from *viburnum grandiflorum* via hydrothermal method

2.4 Measurement of Quantum Yield (QY)

The well established relative method was adopted to calculate the quantum yield (QY) of Nitrogen & Sulfur Codoped carbon nanodots (N/S-CQDs). A solution of quinine sulfate was dissolved in 0.10 M H₂SO₄ (QY 54 % at 360 nm) was taken as a standard. To avoid reabsorption effect the optical absorbance intensity of both quinine sulfate and N-S Codoped CDs solution must be kept below 0.10 at the excitation wavelength the quantum yield of N - CDs was

determined by using the following equation
Scheme 2.3.

$$Q_x = Q_s \times I_x / I_s \times A_s / A_x \times n_x^2 / n_s^2$$

2.5 Detection of Fe³⁺ Ions

The metal ion sensing performance of N,S-doped carbon dots (N,S CDs) was evaluated in aqueous media using various metal ions, where fluorescence measurements were recorded at an excitation wavelength of 360 nm. Among all tested ions, Fe³⁺ caused the most pronounced fluorescence quenching, demonstrating the high

selectivity and sensitivity of N,S CDs toward Fe^{3+} detection. Subsequent Fe^{3+} sensing studies showed a good linear fluorescence response in the concentration range of 0–800 μM , with a low limit of detection of $\sim 0.4 \mu M$. The sensing performance was further validated in tap water samples after filtration, confirming practical applicability. Interference studies with

mixed metal ions revealed negligible fluorescence quenching in the absence of Fe^{3+} , while the presence of Fe^{3+} resulted in nearly complete quenching. Visual observation under UV and daylight conditions further confirmed the selective fluorescence quenching behavior of N,S CDs toward Fe^{3+} ions.

Figure 2.2. (a) N,S-CDs under UV light (365 nm); (b) comparison of tap water containing N,S-CDs with and without Fe^{3+} ions under daylight conditions

Figure 2.3. Comparison of N,S-CDs fluorescence in the presence and absence of Fe^{3+} ions under UV light (365 nm).

Figure 2.4 (c) Photograph of simple CDs from *Viburnum grandiflorum* under UV light

(d) Photograph of N-S CDs under UV Light

(c) Photograph of metal salts used for the preparation of metal solution used in experiment

Figure 2.3: Comparison of the N-S Codope CDs in the presence and absence of Fe³⁺ ion under UV light of 365 nm. Left side tube contain Fe³⁺ ion in N/S -CDs solution (quenching occur) while there is no Fe³⁺ ion in right side N-CDs solution

Figure 2.4 (c) Photograph of simple CDs *Viburnum grandiflorum* under UV light

(d) Photograph of N-S CDs under from UV Light

Graph 1: UV-Visible Absorption Data of N/S-CDs

Graph 2: Fluorescence Emission Data of N/S-CDs

3.5 Conclusion:

In this work we have prepared N/S C Dots via facile environmental friendly hydrothermal method using *Viburnum grandiflorum* fruit a novel carbon source and two doping agents L-cysteine as Sulphur source and ethylenediamine as nitrogen source. The obtained N/S doped C-Dots demonstrated to have photo stability with water solubility and most importantly they have good sensitive detection property for the Fe³⁺ ions. It was found that for enhancing PL performance of carbon dots for metal ion detection the doping agent play a key role. Moreover, the detailed study on interaction of N/S CDs solution against Fe³⁺ at various concentration ranges indicate that the solution of Fe³⁺ quenched N/S CDs could be used to detect Fe³⁺ at both very low and high concentrated solutions. The above results show that obtained N/S C-Dots could hold a great potential for a many heavy metals detection applications. Finally, we can say that for developing a great variety of low cost and sensitive sensors for water detection this work can provide a new approach.

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